

an intuitive approach to indeterminate forms

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1 Abstract

This algorithm was developed by using the fact that functions approach their linear approximations when sufficiently zoomed in at that point. After that, simple translations can be used to remove any indeterminate forms.

2 Formulation

Let's take the following general form:

$$L = \lim_{x \rightarrow a} \frac{f(x)}{g(x)}, \text{ where } L \rightarrow \frac{0}{0} \quad (1)$$

2.1 alpha

The first step would be to replace both $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ with their linear approximations at a . We can safely do this because sufficiently zooming into the functions near a point will make them linear. All functions are linear at infinitesimal scales. We can calculate these linear approximations by first calculating the derivatives of the functions at point a i.e. $f'(a)$ and $g'(a)$, and then substituting these as gradients into the equation of a straight line $y = mx + c$. The resulting form would be as follows.

$$L = \lim_{x \rightarrow a} \frac{m_1x + c}{m_2x + d}, \text{ where } c, d \in \{constants\} \quad (2)$$

2.2 beta

The second step would be to translate both $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ such that their point of intersection, which is also the same point the limit approaches to, moves to zero. This can easily be done by tweaking the input x to the functions by a certain amount. After the translation, the constants should disappear and the form should look something like shown below.

$$L = \lim_{x' \rightarrow 0} \frac{m_1x'}{m_2x'} \quad (3)$$

2.3 gamma

After the cancellation, we would be left with the ratio of gradients, which is also equal to the ratio of derivatives of the two functions.

$$L = \frac{m_1}{m_2} = \frac{f'(a)}{g'(a)} \quad (4)$$

This above form is known as the **l'hospital's rule**. The intuitive reasoning we developed has led us to it.

3 Example

Evaluate the following limit:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow -5} \frac{x^2 - 25}{x + 5}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx}(x^2 - 25) = 2x \implies 2(-5) = -10 \text{ at point } x = -5$$

$$x^2 - 25 \approx -10x - 50 \text{ near point } x = -5$$

$$L = \lim_{x \rightarrow -5} -\frac{10x + 50}{x + 5}$$

By using the coordinate transformation $x = x' - 5$, we can shift the point to origin.

$$L = \lim_{x' \rightarrow 0} -\frac{10x'}{x'} = -10 \text{ Answer}$$

4 Works used

[1] Thomas, George Brinton, et al. Thomas' calculus. Addison-Wesley, 2005.